

Margaret Atwood's *the Handmaid's Tale*: A Representation of Woman's Oppression in the Gileadean Patriarchal Society

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Abstract

Feminism talks of the equality of men and women. It is the core belief in and advocacy of economic, social and political equality of both the sexes. Atwood's "The Handmaid's Tale" explores her vision of feministic ideology. This paper deals with the idea of the status of women in the society of Gilead. She portrays the oppression of women through the character of Offred and other female characters in the Gileadean patriarchal society. Atwood comments the recent tendency of feminism through satire to give the awareness on how the feminist visions end up in dystopias.

Keywords: feminism, oppression, patriarchy, gender, equality, society.

Feminism is defined as the advocacy of the rights of women on the foundation of parity between the male and female in the society. It is also the theory of social, political and economic parity for women and men. Feminism aims towards parity and not for the superiority of women.

The literature of feminism depicts ideas or characters that attempts to engage in changing the norms of gender. The feminist literature helps to identify the unequal female roles to those of male. It is particularly portrayed the results to female, male, families and societies as not desirable. It is the necessity of analyzing the feminism and feminist criticism in literature to promote awareness that the female individual beings are no replaceable objects that should be controlled by male. The critics of feminist literature examine how the literature works are influenced by a male dominated society.

The literature from 1700 to 2010 is popular with the works of fiction, criticism and theory which concerning with one subject: feminism. Some of the popular feminist literature books are Mary Wollstonecraft's *A Vindication of the Rights of Women*, Virginia Woolf's *A Room of One's Own*, Bell Hooks' *Feminism is for Everybody*, Kate Bornstein's *Gender Outlaw*, Roxane Gray's *Bad Feminist*, Louis May Alcott's *Little Women*, Sylvia Plath's *Bell Jar*, Simon De Beauvoir's *The Second Sex*, Margaret Atwood's *The Handmaid's Tale*, Betty Friedan's *The Feminine Mystique*, Alice Walker's *In Search of Our Mothers' Gardens*. Doris Lessing's *The Golden Notebook*.

The writers give voices and perspectives on the specific theme of feminism. The authors focus a wide range of written expression in common is a depiction on the female experience. They dealt with how it alters, expands and evolves.

This paper deals with the idea of Margaret Atwood's *The Handmaid's Tale* represents the oppression of women in the Gileadean society of patriarchy. She criticizes the view of feminism through satire. Margaret Atwood is one of the popular Canadian writers in English Literature. She is a Canadian novelist, poet, essayist and literary critic. She got so many awards for her works. She focuses the variety of themes like identity, religion and gender.

Atwood is actively engaged in Politics and feminist movement of Canada. In her works, she deals with the issues of social and political. She focuses the relation of male and female and the basic rights of human in the society. The gender issue is the major concern of Atwood. She depicts the female characters in her works which always focused on a search for identity in an oppressed patriarchal society. She is famous for the theme of oppression. She represents the gender, the exploitation and the oppression of female, especially on women's body. In her novels, she centers on the pain and suffering of female characters.

The Handmaid's Tale emphasizes on the main concern of gender and their roles. In the Gileadean society, Women are destitute of their freedom and pushed to serve for their state in many ways. Women are dominated by the male people in the society of patriarchy. She illustrates the patriarchy and how it reflects the American political ideology of that period. It shows clearly on the rules of patriarchy, husbands' or fathers' dominance in the family. Women are dominated and controlled by men and consider them as a means of mass production. Atwood talks about the situation of women in society and the discrimination they faced because of their sex.

The story shows the position of oppressed women in the Gileadean patriarchal society. In this society, women are diminished the status of slavery and for the means of reproduction and are the man's use. The story is a nightmare of dystopia. The women's freedom denies and enslaves to the focus of biology. The author depicts women as an ovary, a two-leg wombs and the female in Gilead. In the Gileadean patriarchal society, the state manipulates and controls the biology of women.

Atwood bring about a society in which the biology of women and their procreating function. It is as the main root for the oppression in the place. Gilead diminishes the slavery status of women. They are the machines of reproduction and are determined based on their biology as Offred emphasizes:

We are all for breeding purposes. We aren't concubines, geisha girls, courtesans. On the contrary: everything possible has been done to remove us from that category there is supposed to be nothing entertaining about us [...] we are two legged wombs, that's all: sacred vessels, ambulatory chalices (*The Handmaid's Tale* 13).

Women are considered as ambulatory wombs. Women in Gilead are destitute on the identity of gender. They do not have the opportunity on the capacity of bearing the child. The novel clearly reveals the key element on the oppression of women. Maternity is the task of women's biology in the Gileadean society. Women are under estimated and worthy only for their capacity of fertility. The Commander gives grounds for the Gileadean rules to Offred by asserting that the women's new state will be kept safe or will be able to "fulfill their

biological destinies in peace with full support and encouragement” (*The Handmaid’s Tale* 219). In another way Atwood explicits women are just for serving men and they are imprisoned by their body, as Offred states “something that determines me so completely” (*The Handmaid’s Tale* 69).

The novel can be seen that the handmaids are treated as “Other”. They are the relative beings. Women are described by their capacity, their biology for their reproduction. They are not basically treated as human being. The Handmaids are mostly deemed as the enormous oppressive group compared to the other groups of women in Gileadean society. In a patriarchal domestic brutality Offred is a prisoner. She spends most of her time in bedroom. The bedroom is the prison for her. She considers her bedroom:

I don’t want to do it at once, I wanted to make it last. I divided the room into sections, in my head; I allowed myself one section a day. This one section I would examine with the greatest minutes: the unevenness of the plaster under the top coat of paint ... she was careless. (*The Handmaid’s Tale* 58).

It shows the present dissatisfaction life of Offred. She is considered as slave and persecuted in the regime of Gilead. The Gileadean society considers the handmaids as immature. They are treated as children and kept vulnerable. Women in the society belong only to the Commanders. Women are also treated as their own properties. The regime of Gilead successfully steals women and their identities. The regime transforms women into the replaceable objects in the economy of phallogocentric throughout the novel. Their real names are also deprived from them. Offred states: “my name is not Offred, I have another name, which nobody uses now because it’s forbidden” (*The Handmaid’s Tale* 88). She suggests that the Handmaids are destituted of their identity, because their name is her or his identity.

The names of the Handmaids are just tools. It reveals to whom they part of. One of the foundations of patriarchal society of Gilead is totally a male ownership. It also highlights the destitution of the self-identity of women. Handmaids are the slaves of sex and machines of fertility. They are fully controlled under the males of high class in Gilead.

The Gilead’s biological mothers are women who were compelled and got education from the Red Centre. They should be ready to take their role of Handmaids before they are placed into the household of Commanders. Atwood focuses the women’s oppression in a biological way throughout the institutionalized society of maternity in the Gilead Society.

The exploitation of women by men in Gilead especially Handmaids are forced to take the roles of maternal. The society expects them to do in many ways. An institutionalized maternity explores the oppression of women in biology and is shown through the life of Handmaids. They must understand that this is their fate and cannot have the rights of refusing it. It reveals in one of the meetings of Offred and Commander, she states, “we are for breeding purposes [...] we are two legged wombs, that’s all: sacred vessels, ambulatory chalices” (*The Handmaid’s Tale* 139), It shows that all handmaids and Offred agree their roles and have a hope to be pregnated “I have viable ovaries. I have one more chance” (*The Handmaid’s Tale* 145). Women accept this view of maternity is their destiny of biology.

The Handmaids are persecuted, exploited and ill treated because of their body of fertility by male people. Offred illustrates the situation: “resign my body freely, to the use of others. They can do what they like with me. I am object” (*The Handmaid's Tale* 282).

All female bodies are focused as the object of inheritance in the Gileadean society. This state extends the domination of male and aims to bring the power structures of Gilead. The women are taught how to play their role of maternal. The aunts fulfill the duty of the handmaids. In this story, the values of the handmaids are reduced to their body. The womb is being trained in the Red Center. The hands and feet of Handmaids are useless organs, their wombs are only considered as worthy for fertility. Aunt Lydia says the handmaids to think of themselves like seeds. Seed signifies the offspring. This is the only prominent thing in Gilead. Jezebel is a hidden household that explores the strong sense of slavery on women's sexual in Gilead, as Moira describes “Butch Paradise” (*The Handmaid's Tale* 249). Offred is illtreated. She is like a prostitute when she becomes Commander's mistress; she is dressed as a prostitute by the Commander when they want to go to the Jezebel's.

Margaret Atwood's novel *The Handmaids Tale* is basically dealt with objectification of female in the Gileadean patriarchal society. The novel is the story of the oppression of women, where female treats as slaves and subjected to the complete control in every situation of their lives. Atwood brings the second status of women in the society. She explores the female as the second sex and other. Atwood defines a society in which female are physically and mentally enslaved. Women are treated as slaves and men are their masters. In this novel, Atwood portrays a society of patriarchy and in which women are not worthy and they are for only reproduction.

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